

DEVELOPMENT OF TEXTILE-BASED TEMPERATURE SENSOR

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Abstract: *Body temperature is an important physiological signal in terms of heat, cold stress and comfort aspects. The aim of this study was to develop weft knitted temperature- sensing fabric along with application of welding technology. Temperature sensing structures have been realised by knitting conductive yarns into the textile structure. The working principle of knitted sensors is based on the inherent tendency of conductive yarn to respond changes in temperature according to its electrical resistance. Knitted samples have been manufactured by alternating base material properties and conductive yarn linear resistance. This affected sensing properties of sensing structures. While applying of welding technology has resulted in increase in nominal resistance values, it also affected linearity of the sensors.*

Keywords: *Temperature sensing fabric, flat-bed knitting technology, welding, knitted sensor*

1. Introduction

Benefitting from the continual developments in science and technology, textile products are becoming ever more functional and clothing offers new features rather than just providing protection against environmental conditions or fulfilling fashion needs [1-3]. There is on- going research in the integration of sensing functionality into traditional textile structures and these new textile products integrated with sensing properties may be defined as smart textiles, intelligent textiles, or functional textiles. In the wearable electronics approach, the functional elements of the system are mostly rigid and bulky electronic parts and there is little integration between the electronic components and the clothing of the user. In contrast, the e-textile approach aims to minimize the number and size of rigid electronic parts in the system in order to create truly smart textile clothing. Apart from individual efforts, due to increasing attention on wearable health monitoring systems (WHMS), some European Union funded projects have been performed in the last decade. Projects have focused mainly on monitoring vital signs of people in daily life or in extreme conditions, and different kinds of prototypes have been manufactured [4-5]. In some cases, sensing components have been used as attachable components to the system [6]. Also, sensing parts have been realized as an integral part of the garment by using conductive yarns. Thus, the creation of sensing modules as integrated textile structures has facilitated manufacturing of washable smart garments. Although textile-based sensing technology covers different types of sensors, textile-based temperature sensing technology is not studied comprehensively as compared to respiration monitoring or ECG monitoring. Some studies have been conducted in respect of the creation of textile based sensing structures. Husain et al. developed a temperature sensing fabric using the knitting route. Fine metal wires were laid in a double layer of knitted fabric. The working principle of the sensors is based on resistance-temperature variation [7-8]. Locher et al. developed a temperature sensor through weaving. In this case, insulated copper wires were used as sensing elements along with polyester yarns [9]. Sibinski et al. developed a yarn based temperature sensor using thermo-resistive paste [10]. They examined different kinds of fibre types for use as the substrate material before finally using PVDF monofilament due to its higher flexibility and lower mass factor coupled with it offering suitable levels of resistance.

The creation of sensing structures at the fabric level is the most common method that is employed and knitting technology is widely preferred as it offers a relatively high level of elasticity which is a need for human body applications. Thus, in this study flat-bed knitting technology was employed to produce temperature sensing fabric structures and the working principle of the sensing fabrics is based on the inherent propensity of conductive yarn to respond to changes in temperature with corresponding variation in its electrical resistance. However, the main drawback for proposed knitted structures as temperature sensing applications that knitted fabrics were also highly sensitive to strain. Thus, in order to prevent this problem welding technology has been applied to stabilize sensing areas for temperature sensing application

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Production of knitted sensors

In order to manufacture knitted sensors, a Shima-Seiki 12S 12-gauge computerized flat-bed knitting machine was employed. Mechanical movements within the knitting machine are controlled electronically using CAD/CAM systems. For the production of the sensors, packages of both non-conductive and conductive yarn were located on top of the knitting machine. Yarns were threaded to the knitting machine using a conventional route, with the yarns passing through ceramic guides, knot catchers and cymbal tensioners. The knitted sensors were designed by using Shima-Seiki Knit Paint software as illustrated in Figure 1 prior to being manufactured on the knitting machine. At the technical face of the fabric, silver plated nylon yarns were used to create conductive loops. A single design of knitted temperature-sensing fabric was devised. Alternating yarn type and applying of ultrasonic welding technology created different variations of the basic knitted sensor. Table 1 below shows that the materials used during the manufacturing stage of sensing fabrics. The eight groups of temperature sensing fabrics were manufactured using an interlock arrangement and the conductive yarn was embedded into this interlock structure in a series of single loops.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of knitted sensor design showing design showing the geometry of the conductive yarn.

In figure 1, while orange color knitted loops represents the conductive yarn within the temperature sensing fabric, rest of the knitted loops represents non-conductive yarns.

Table 1. Conductive and non-conductive yarn parameters for manufacturing of knitted sensors

Structure type no	Base Material	Conductive yarn Type	Base fabric yarn density	Conductive yarn density	Conductive yarn linear resistance
1	m-aramid 100%+lycra	Silver coated polyamide 1	166 dtex +70 denier	235 dtex-4 ply	50 ohm/m
2	m-aramid 100%+lycra	Silver coated polyamide 2	166 dtex+70 denier	235 dtex	235 ohm/m
3	Double PA 6.6 covered lycra	Silver coated polyamide 1	800 dtex	235 dtex -4 ply	50 ohm/m
4	Double PA 6.6 covered lycra	Silver coated polyamide 2	800 dtex	235 dtex	235 ohm/m
5	Single PA 6.6 covered lycra	Silver coated polyamide 1	576 dtex	235 dtex -4ply	50 ohm/m
6	Single PA 6.6 covered lycra	Silver coated polyamide 2	576 dtex	235 dtex	235 ohm/m
Structure type no	Base material	Conductive yarn type		Welding tape	
7	m-aramid 100%+lycra	Silver coated polyamide 1		Welding tape 1:transparent-ST804	
8	m-aramid 100%+lycra	Silver coated polyamide 1		Welding tape 2: -ST306 Grey	

2.2. Test Methodology

2.2.1. Test rig components

A Custom made hotplate with dimensions of 210 x 294 x 10 mm³ was used as a heating source for the test rig that provides contact heat to the samples. 12 resistors are attached on its lower surface of the aluminum plate and Maximum temperature of the plate was set as 45 °C. Figure 2 shows schematic diagram of the hotplate with its resistors and full test rig for temperature and resistance measurement.

a

b

Figure 2. (a) Schematic diagram of hotplate (b) Full test rig

Full test rig consists of a hot plate, power supply, electrical multi meter, temperature recorder and thermocouple.

2.2.2. Measurement methodology

Fabric samples were located on hotplate surface. A thermocouple was attached on surface of the sensing structure in order to measure change in temperature. Electrical Multi meter was connected to fabric sample for resistance measurement. Readings were taken for 30 minutes at 0.1 °C intervals.

3. Results

In total, 8 types of samples were tested and 2 types of them were welded samples. As seen graphics in Figure 3, all the samples has negative correlation between the applied heat and change in resistance. Although sensing structures have same knitted design, they showed different experimental sensitivity i.e. the rate of change of resistance with respect to temperature. This can be attributed to the effect of material parameters on sensing properties of knitted samples.

On the other hand, type 1 sensor was chosen as a reference structure for welding application. Two different type of welding tape were applied to the sensing area of the structure. Application of welding tape was resulted in increase of the nominal resistance of the sensing structures. However, it affected sensing linearity slightly. Thus, welding parameters should be adjusted carefully for this specific application.

Figure 3. Resistance vs Temperature graphics of knitted sensors

4. Conclusion

In this study, textile-based temperature sensor and the effect of material types and welding application on its sensor properties have been presented. A strong relationship has been established between the sensor characteristics and the production parameters. Variations in conductive yarn electrical resistance and non – conductive base material type have greatly affected the sensors` linear range and sensitivity values. Also, welding technology has been used in order to create stable sensing structures against strain deformations. However, This resulted in increase in nominal resistance value and decrease in linearity of the sensing structure.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 644268. The article describes the part of the project which was realized by the Department of Textile Engineering of ITU, and Technical Education Institute of Pireus.

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